

Revision of the Ariantinae. 5. The genus *Dinarica* Kobelt, 1902 (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Helicidae)¹

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Native to the Balkan region, species of the genus *Dinarica* are revised based on conchological characters. In addition, the anatomy of the genital organs and some selected morphological features of the body are discussed. Localities are listed and the current-distribution of the species presented on maps. The shells of all taxa recognized as valid, including the shells of many synonymous species, are illustrated. The new species, *Dinarica* (*D.*) *skutariensis* spec. nov., is described. The differences in the genital organs of the species *D.* (*Sabljaria*) *stenomphala* to *Dinarica* (*Dinarica*) s. str. corroborate the separate position of the subgenus *Sabljaria*.

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INTRODUCTION

As a result of the present revision of the recent species of the genus *Dinarica*, five taxa are recognized as valid species, one of which is described as new to science. Due to their large size, *Dinarica* species are easily spotted by collectors. Thus, *Dinarica pouzolzii* (Deshayes, 1831) frequently occurs in mollusc collections. Due to their morphological variability,

numerous taxa have been established for this species. Most of the taxa (12 in number) were described by Bourguignat in 1888, the founder of the Nouvelle École. He assigned names to every noticeable change in shape or colour. Most of the taxa described by him originate from an approximately 70 km long coastal strip between Dubrovnik (= Ragusa) and Kotor (= Cattaro). In addition, there is the general tendency for *D. pouzolzii* to have smaller, depressed, widely umbilicated shells in the mountains more inland, and larger specimens with a more spherical shape, higher whorls and a narrower umbilicus occurring on the coast (see also comments under *D. pouzolzii*). The other *Dinarica* species are less widespread and less variable. Only a few individuals are known from the two species, *D.* (*D.*) *albanica* and *D.* (*D.*) *skutariensis* spec. nov. Nonetheless, they can be clearly distinguished from other *Dinarica* species by their shell features. Recently, the phylogenetic system of the Ariantinae was improved by a multigene analysis of mitochondrial and nuclear genes (Groenenberg et al., 2016) whereby the separation of *Sabljaria* as the sister taxon of *Dinarica* was proposed. This result is supported by the morphology of the genital organs of *D. stenomphala* presented here.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The type specimens of most *Dinarica* taxa can be found in the MHNG, MNHN, SMF and ZMB. They were loaned to NMBE or SMF, compared and one specimen of the type series per taxon was photographed. In addition, shells and bodies of *Dinarica* species from other museums and private collections stored, dry or preserved, were examined. During own collecting trips, the countries of former Yugoslavia and Greece were visited. All shell measurements in mm.

Abbreviations for collections: E = private collection Z. Eröss, Budapest; F = private collection W. Fauer, now in Zoological Museum of Hamburg; Hu = private collection A. Hunyadi, Budapest; HNHM = Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest; IZPAN = Polska Akademia Nauk, Insty-

¹ SUBAI, P. & NEUBERT, E. (2016). Revision of the Ariantinae. 4. The genus *Faustina* Kobelt 1904 (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Helicidae). – *Archiv für Molluskenkunde*, 145 (1): 85–110.

tut Zoologii, Warszawa; Maa = private collection W.J.M. Maassen (now in RMNH); MHNG = Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva; MMB = Munkácsi Mihály Múzeum, Békéscsaba; MMNH = Macedonian Museum of Natural History, Skopje; MNHN = Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris; NMBE = Natural History Museum, Bern; NMW = Natural History Museum, Vienna; NMWE = collection Edlauer in NMW; NMWK = collection Klemm in NMW; NMWR = collection Rušňov in NMW; RMNH = Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie, Leiden, now incorporated in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden; S = private collection P. Subai, Aachen, now in NMBE; SMF = Senckenberg Museum, Frankfurt a. M.; ZMB = Zoological Museum of the Humboldt University, Berlin.

Additional abbreviations: AD = diameter of aperture; AH = height of the aperture; alc. = specimen preserved in alcohol; D = shell diameter; FYROM = Former Yugoslavian Republic of Macedonia; H = height of the shell; juv. = juvenile specimen.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Class Gastropoda Cuvier, 1795

Order Stylommatophora A. Schmidt, 1855

Family Helicidae Rafinesque, 1815

Genus *Dinarica* Kobelt, 1902; subgenus *Dinarica* s. str.

Dinarica Kobelt, 1902: 60, 61. Type species (by tautonomy):

Helix dinarica Bourguignat, 1888 (= *Helix pouzolzii* Deshayes, 1831).

The characteristic features of the shell of *Dinarica* are as follows: shell spherical-conical to strongly depressed conical; colour horn-yellow with a brownish tinge or brown, with one to three bands, marginal bands often blurred; shell surface with irregular, sometimes coarse radial bands and dense spiral grooves; whorls 4.75–6.25; umbilicus 3–9.4 mm wide, from narrow, stitch-shaped to wide, perspective; aperture round to transversely oval, cut out on the left side, with the apertural insertions 7–16 mm apart; apertural margin sharp to blunt, moderately dilated.

Anatomical features: mantle on the last whorl bearing irregular, blurred, elongated grey-brown spots; secondary ureter completely open; glandulae bifurcated (more rarely un-bifurcated or with 3 branches); shaft of the bursa copulatrix $\frac{1}{4}$ – $\frac{1}{2}$ of the length of the pedunculus; diverticulum 1.1–1.6 times longer than pedunculus + vesicle; flagellum 1.5–4 times longer than penis + epiphallus; penis retractor muscles adhere at the centre of the epiphallus; dart large, broad, straight; its apex lanceolate, 36–43 % of total length; atrial papilla in the centre of the atrium spreading in the direction of the penial lumen, its highest point the bulge-like raised outer edge; penial papilla short, bluntly conical, opening in a lateral longitudinal fissure.

Fig. 1. *Dinarica (Dinarica) albanica* (Jaekel, 1954). Holotype *Helicigona stenomphala albanica*, ZMB 101242, Albania, Berisha, D = 37 mm. Photo original size.

Dinarica (Dinarica) albanica (Jaekel, 1954)

Figs 1, 35

Helicigona stenomphala albanica Jaekel, 1954: 87–88, fig. 23. Type locality: “Berischa am mittleren Drin, nördliches Albanien”. Holotype ZMB 101242.

Chresonyms:

Helicigona albanica – Dhora & Welter-Schultes, 1996: 161 + map; Welter-Schultes, 2012: 587 + map.

Diagnosis. — Shell spherical-conical, yellowish-horny, without banding; umbilicus narrow, punctate, half covered; aperture transversely oval.

Description. — The only shell known is slightly spherical-conical; shell colour yellowish-horny without banding; protoconch 1.75 whorls (although eroded, traces of fine radial sculpture can be recognized at the edges); body whorls sculptured with dense, slightly raised, curved, irregular radial stripes; last whorl with spiral grooves, sometimes slightly recessed and dense; radial stripes becoming increasingly coarser with increasing whorl numbers; shell whorls 6, regularly increasing; last whorl is 1.75 times as wide as the penultimate one, sloping down slowly in a slight curve before the aperture; suture moderately deep with an irregular edge; umbilicus narrow, roughly cylindrical, hardly increasing in width at the beginning, widening to twice its width at the last whorl (3.8 mm wide); aperture transversely oval, slightly flattened at the top, cut out on the left side; insertions 10.7 mm apart, connected by a thin callus; apertural margin sharp, widening up from 1.3–2 mm at the side and at the base, strongly extending towards the umbilicus, covering it by half.

Shell measurements (n = 1): H = 25; D = 36.4; AH = 16.8; AD = 22.8.

Anatomical remarks. — So far, no living animal was recorded.

Differential diagnosis. — *Dinarica stenomphala* is smaller, with a narrower umbilicus. The umbilicus is covered by the extended apertural margin except for a slit. The insertions of the aperture in *D. stenomphala* are further apart. *Dinarica skutariensis* has three broad, brown bands. Its surface is covered with coarser growth lines. Its umbilicus is wider and barely covered by the apertural margin. Its aperture is almost circular, barely oblique. *Dinarica serbica* is considerably smaller, more depressed, with three broad, dark brown bands. The umbilicus of *D. serbica* is barely covered by the apertural margin. Its surface with coarser growth lines and with clearly deepened spiral grooves. Its aperture is smaller and almost circular.

Remarks. — The holotype of *Helicigona stenomphala albanica* Jaeckel (1954: 87, fig. 23) is a large, bandless specimen. It is the only individual of this species known to date.

Helicigona stenomphala albanica is not a primary homonym of *Campylaea (Dinarica) montenegrina* var. *albanica* Kobelt, 1902, nor a secondary homonym, as there is no chresonym of *albanica* Kobelt, 1902 in combination with *Helicigona*. And since *albanica* Kobelt, 1902 is a synonym of *pouzolzii*, it cannot be used as a valid name in combination with *Dinarica*. Therefore, no new name (nomen novum) is introduced.

Distribution. — Only known from the type locality (Berischa = Berisha or Berishë = 42.1705° 19.8004°; eastern bank of the Drin), which is approximately 30 km NE of Shkodër in northern Albania.

Dinarica (Dinarica) pouzolzii (Deshayes, 1831)

Figs 2-25

Helix pouzolzii Payraudeau, 1826: 102–103. Nomen nudum. [“sur le Mont-Cagno, entre Figari et Porto-Vecchio”].

Helix pouzolzi Deshayes, 1831, Mag. Zool., 1 (Première Partie [= Classe V; Mollusques]; livr. 4): pl. 30 (as *pouzolzi* mentioned on the bottom of the plate) + text (as *pouzolzii*). Type locality: “elle n’a encore été trouvée qu’en Corse”. Holotype MNHN (Fig. 2). Note: in almost all subsequent literature earlier than 1995 the spelling *pouzolzi* is used, whereas after 1995 the spelling *pouzolzii* is used, which is here followed.

Helix montenegrina Rossmässler, 1836: 1. Type locality: not mentioned. Holotype SMF 5267 (Fig. 8) “Montenegro”. Note: name attributed to Ziegler.

Helix gravosaensis Rossmässler, 1836: 1. Type locality: not mentioned. Note: name attributed to Megerle von Mühlfeld.

Helix varronis Cantraine, 1836: 111–112, pl. 4 figs 1–3. Type locality: “dans le territoire de Ragusa”. Type material: not researched.

Helix macarana H. Beck, 1837: 26. Type locality: not mentioned. Note: name attributed to Megerle von Mühlfeld.

Helix pouzolzi var. *minor* Rossmässler, 1838: 15, pl. 33 fig. 459. Type locality: not mentioned. Holotype SMF 5267.

Campylaea pouzolzi var. *trifasciata* Brusina, 1869: 56. Type locality: not mentioned. Note: name attributed to Bielz.

Campylaea pouzolzi var. *bifasciata* Brusina, 1869: 56. Type locality: “près de Raguse”.

Campylaea pouzolzi var. *unifasciata* Brusina, 1869: 56. Type locality: “sur la route Autrichienne qui conduit de Cattaro au Montenegro”. Note: name attributed to Pfeiffer.

Campylaea pouzolzi var. *obscura* Brusina, 1869: 56. Type locality: not mentioned. Note: name attributed to Bielz.

Campylaea pouzolzi var. *unicolor* Brusina, 1869: 56. Type locality: not mentioned. Note: name attributed to Pfeiffer.

Helix pouzolzi var. *bosniensis* Kobelt, 1871: 71. Type locality: “aus dem Bosnathal”. Holotype SMF 5198/1 (Fig. 5), Travnik, coll. Moellendorff, paratypes coll. Moellendorff, SMF 29719/4, ex Moellendorff, coll. Kobelt, SMF 29811/1 (Icon. Fig. 985).

Helix pancici Kobelt, 1872: 131–132, pl. 4 figs 10–12. Type locality: “Serbia”. Syntypes SMF 5200 (Fig. 23) “Serbia”, SMF 5201/2 “Südliches Serbien”, leg. Pančić, coll. Moellendorff. Note: misspelled as *Helix paucici* by Tryon, 1888: 88, pl. 21 figs 69–71.

Helix (Campylaea) pouzolzi var. *bosnensis* Möllendorff, 1873: 36. Note: unjustified emendation for *bosniensis* Kobelt, 1871.

Helix soccaliana Letourneux, 1887: 238. Type locality: “Sommet du Santi-Deca, dans l’île de Corfou”. Syntype MHNG 17188/1 (Fig. 16).

Helix adriatica Bourguignat, 1888: 226–228. Type locality: “en Dalmatie, dans toutes les contrées littorales de Cattaro à Spalato des jardins de Salona, dans le voisinage des Sorgente”. Syntype MHNG 17172/1 (Fig. 12) “Environ de Cattaro” (see remarks); syntypes MHNG 17171/5 “Jardin de Salona”.

Helix diocletiana Bourguignat, 1888: 234–235, pl. 3 figs 5–7. Type locality: “Environs de Spalato”. Holotype MHNG 17180 (Fig. 4).

Helix dinarica Bourguignat, 1888: 217–219, pl. 2 figs 1–3. Type locality: “Sous les détritux humides et les plantes dans le district de Cattaro”. Syntypes MHNG 17178/1 (Fig. 11), MHNG 17179/1 “Cattaro”.

Helix brenoica Bourguignat, 1888: 242–243. Type locality: “en Dalmatie, de la vallée de Breno, vit également dans les districts de Raguse et de Cattaro”. Syntype MHNG 17174/1 (Fig. 20) “Cattaro” (see remarks).

Helix biagioli Bourguignat, 1888: 240–242, pl. 4 figs 5–6. Type locality: “district de Cattaro”. No type specimens

Figs 2-8. *Dinarica (Dinarica) pouzolzii* (Deshayes, 1831). **2.** Holotype *Helix pouzolzii* MNHN, without locality, D = 43.5 mm; **3.** HHNM 95923, East-Albanian form, Periferi Dibrë, Arras 2 km of the Kukës-Peshkopi country road in direction Cidhnë, D = 33 mm. **4.** Holotype *Helix diocletiana* MHNG 17180, Croatia, “Environs de Spalato”, D = 35.5 mm. **5.** Holotype *Helix pouzolzii* var. *bosniensis* SMF 5198, Travnik, D = 30 mm. **6.** Syntype *Campylaea (Dinarica) moratschensis* SMF 5225, “Moratscha-Thal”, D = 27 mm. **7.** Holotype *Campylaea (Dalmatica) montenegrina* SMF 5226 var. *komensis*, “Moratscha-Thal”, D = 29 mm. **8.** Holotype *Helix montenegrina* “Montenegro” SMF 5267, D = 34.6 mm. Photos original size.

present in coll. Bourguignat in MHNG.

Helix daniloi Bourguignat, 1888: 243. Type locality: “district de Cattaro”. Holotype MHNG 17176 (Fig. 9) “Monténégro”.

Helix horatii Bourguignat, 1888: 238–240, pl. 4 figs 3–4. Type locality: “aux environs de Cattaro”. Holotype MHNG

17181 (Fig. 18) “Cattaro, Dalmatie”.

Helix tchernagorica Bourguignat, 1888: 232–234, pl. 3 figs 3–4. Type locality: “Fentes des rochers le long de la route de Cattaro à Cetinge (Monténégro)”. Syntypes MHNG 17189/2 (Fig. 19) “Mont. au-des. de Cattaro”.

Figs 9-14. *Dinarica* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzii* (Deshayes, 1831). **9.** Holotype *Helix daniloi* MHNG 17176, “district de Cattaro”, D = 43.1 mm. **10.** Syntype *Helix sabljari* MHNG 17187, Bosnia-Herzegovina, “vallee...Narenta”, D = 40.9 mm. **11.** Syntype *Helix dinarica* MHNG 17178, Kotor, D = 41.3 mm. **12.** Syntype *Helix adriatica* MHNG 17171, “Jardin de Salona”, D = 41.1 mm. **13.** Holotype *Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina* var. *bizona* SMF 5220, Montenegro, D = 40.8 mm. **14.** Holotype *Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina* var. *albatica* SMF 5218, D = 32 mm. Photos original size.

Fig. 15. *Dinarica (Dinarica) pouzolzi* (Deshayes, 1831). Croatia, Kupari (= E of Dubrovnik), coll. Maassen (now NNM). **A.** Body. **B.** Genital organs. **C.** Atrial, penial and vaginal lumen. **D.** Dart in two views.

Helix kuzmici Bourguignat, 1888: 219–221, pl. 2 figs 4–6.

Type locality: “dédiée au malacologiste Kuzmic de Raguse, a été recueillie aux environs de cette ville. Les échantillons unicolores proviennent du district de Cattaro” (see remarks). Syntypes MHNG 17183/2 (Fig. 17) “Cattaro, Dalmatie”, MHNG 17182/1 “Ragusa”.

Helix pellanica Bourguignat, 1888: 222–224, pl. 2 figs 7–9.

Type locality: “Dans les détritons fentes de rochers sur les montagnes qui dominant Cattaro”. Holotype MHNG 17186 “rocher au dessus de Cattaro”.

Helix bosnica Bourguignat, 1888: 228–230. Type locality:

“Cette Hélice, répandue dans un grand nombre de localités de la Bosnie, même de la Serbie occidentale, se trouve également dans l’Herzégovine et la Dalmatie, d’où je la connais des environs de Mostar et de Salona”.

Helix cantrainei Bourguignat, 1888: 244, pl. 4 figs 7–8. Type

locality: “district de Raguse”. No type specimens present in coll. Bourguignat in MHNG.

Helix sabljari Bourguignat, 1888: 237–238, pl. 4 figs 1–2.

Type locality: “sur la rive droite de la vallée de la Narenta”. Syntype MHNG 17187/1 (Fig. 10) “sur la rive droite de la vallée de la Narenta”.

Helix [Campylaea, Eucampylaea] pouzolzi var. *silvestris*

Westerlund, 1889: 115. Type locality: “Südl. Serbien”. Holotype SMF 5199 (Fig. 22) “SW-Serbia” ex Moellendorff coll. Kobelt [= Iconographie fig. 984]. Note: refers to Kobelt, 1875: 6, pl. 93 fig. 984 (as *Helix pouzolzi* var.).

Helix [Campylaea, Eucampylaea] pouzolzi var. *major* West-

erlund, 1889: 115. Type locality: not mentioned.

Helix [Campylaea, Eucampylaea] pouzolzi var. *elevatior*

Figs 16-20. *Dinarica (Dinarica) pouzolzii* (Deshayes, 1831). **16.** Syntype *Helix soccaliana* MHNG 17188, “Santi Deca, dans l’île de Corfou”, D = 50.8 mm. **17.** Syntype *Helix kuzmici* MHNG 17183, Croatia, Dubrovnik, D = 48.7 mm. **18.** Holotype *Helix horatii* MHNG 17181, Kotor, D = 50 mm. **19.** Syntype *Helix tchernagorica* MHNG 17189, “Mont. au-des. de Cattaro”, D = 49.1 mm. **20.** Syntype *Helix brenica* MHNG 17174, Kotor, D = 45 mm. Photos original size.

Figs 21–24. *Dinarica* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzii* (Deshayes, 1831). **21.** Holotype *Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina* var. *costellata* SMF 5222, “Montenegro”, D = 34.5 mm. **22.** Holotype *Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *pouzolzi* var. *silvestris* SMF 5199, “SW-Serbia”, D = 32 mm. **23.** Syntype *Helix pancici* SMF 5200, “Serbia”, D = 30 mm. **24.** Syntype *Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina wohlberedti* SMF 5223, “S. Montenegro, Zabljak”, D = 38.2 mm. Photos original size.

Westerlund, 1889: 115. Type locality: not mentioned. Note: name attributed to Brusina.

Helix [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *pouzolzi* var. *depressior* Westerlund, 1889: 115. Type locality: not mentioned. Note: name attributed to Brusina.

Campylaea (*Dinarica*) *moratschensis* Kobelt, 1898: 161–162. Type locality: “Moraca, Montenegro”. Syntypes SMF 5225 (Fig. 6), SMF 29830/2, Morača (= Moratscha, Moratscha-Valley), ex Floericke coll. Kobelt.

Campylaea (*Dalmatica*) *montenegrina* var. *komensis* Kobelt, 1899: 102, pl. 238 fig. 1553. Type locality: “im Moratscha-Thal”. Holotype SMF 5226 (Fig. 7) “im Moratscha-Thal (der Name des das Thal beherrschenden Gebirgsstock Kom)” ex Rolle coll. Moellendorff.

Campylaea (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina wohlberedti* Kobelt, 1902: 65–66, pl. 263 figs 1698–1700. Type locality: “bei Zabljak am Südbhang von Montenegro”. Syntypes SMF 5211/1, 5221/1, 5223/1 (Fig. 24) “S. Montenegro, Zabljak” [Zabljak near Crnojevica].

Campylaea montenegrina var. *costellata* Kobelt, 1902: pl. 265 fig. 1711 (name mentioned on the plate). Type locality:

“kein Fundort angegeben” (see page 66). Holotype SMF 5222 (Fig. 21) “Montenegro”. Note: mentioned as invalid name on page 66 (as *Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina wohlberedti* mut. *costellata*; infrasubspecific rank ICZN Art. 45.5).

Campylaea pouzolzi var. *bizona* Kobelt, 1902: pl. 265 fig. 1713 (name mentioned on the plate). Type locality: “Montenegro” (see page 68 – as *Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina* var.). Holotype SMF 5220 (Fig. 13), leg. Floericke, coll. Kobelt.

Campylaea (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina* var. *albanica* Kobelt, 1902: 69, pl. 266 fig. 1717. Type locality: “Grec in Albanien”. Holotype SMF 5218 (Fig. 14) “Greč (= Grec)” ex Rolle coll. Kobelt.

Chresonyms:

Helix pouzolzii – Deshayes, 1832: 233.

Helix pouzolzi – Rossmässler, 1836: 1, pl. 16 fig. 215; Pfeiffer, 1848: 346; Deshayes, 1840/1850: 59–61 (1850), pl. 69G figs 1–6 (1840); Pfeiffer, 1853: 231; Reeve, 1852: pl. 93 fig. 507; Pfeiffer, 1859: 274; Brusina, 1866: 120; Pfeiffer, 1875: 411–

- 412; Bourguignat, 1890: 124; Brancsik, 1890: 70; Schuberth, 1892: 25, pl. 3 fig. 6 (radula).
- Campylaea pouzolzi* – Brusina, 1869: 52–57; Brusina, 1907: 95; Tomić, 1959: 21 (partim).
- Helix* (*Campylaea*) *pouzolzi* – Möllendorff, 1873: 36.
- Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *pouzolzi* – Tryon, 1888: 87, pl. 22 fig. 75; Westerlund, 1889: 115.
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzii* – Kobelt, 1902: 60–65, pl. 261 figs 1688–1690, pl. 262 figs 1691–1693.
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzi* – Wohlberedt, 1909: 632–646 (with numerous forms and varieties, but without subspec. *serbica*), pl. 47 figs 21–30, pl. 48 figs 31–50, 52–55, pl. 49 figs 59–60.
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzi* – Sturany & Wagner, 1914: 48, pl. 4 figs 26a–d (genital organs, dart, jaw, radula); Soós, 1924: 195.
- Helicigona* [*Campylaea*] *pouzolzi* – Hesse, 1931: 67–68, pl. 16 figs 7 (mantle), 8 (genital organs).
- Helicigona pouzolzi* – Jaeckel & Schmidt, 1961: 69; Roding, 1966: 136.
- Helicigona pouzolzii* – Dhora & Welter-Schultes, 1996: 165 + map; Welter-Schultes, 2012: 598 + figs (shell; distribution).
- Helicigona pouzolzi pouzolzi* – Knipper, 1939: 400–401, fig. 26 (distribution); Jaeckel, 1954: 87.
- Dinarica* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzii* – Groenenberg et al., 2016: 56, figs 3.21 (shell), 4.23 (genitals).
- Dinarica pouzolzii* – Gojšina et al., 2025: 572–574, figs 71, 73D–F (shell), 76 (distribution).
- Helix pouzolzi* var. – Kobelt, 1875: 6, pl. 93 fig. 984.
- Campylaea pouzolzi* var. – Pavlović, 1912: 74–75 (partim).
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzi* (var. *sylvestris*, Westerlund?) – Kobelt, 1902: 69, pl. 266 fig. 1718 (figure caption as “*Camp. montenegrina* var. *sylvestris*”).
- Helix pancici* – Kobelt, 1875: 6, pl. 93 fig. 983; Bourguignat, 1888: 221–222.
- Helix* (*Campylaea*) *pancici* – Kobelt, 1895: 798, pl. 219 figs 7–8.
- Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *pancici* – Westerlund, 1889: 116.
- Helix montenegrina* – Bourguignat, 1888: 224–226.
- Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *pouzolzi* var. *montenegrina* – Tryon, 1888: 88, pl. 22 fig. 76; Westerlund, 1889: 115 (partim).
- Helix pouzolzi* var. *montenegrina* – Brancsik, 1890: 70.
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzi* var. *montenegrina* – Sturany, 1913: 50.
- Helicigona pouzolzi montenegrina* – Knipper, 1939: 402–404, fig. 26 (distribution).
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *montenegrina* var. – Kobelt, 1902: 68, pl. 264 figs 1706–1707, 1710.
- Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *pouzolzi* var. *bosniensis* – Tryon, 1888: 88, pl. 22 fig. 77.
- Helix pouzolzi* var. *bosniensis* – Brancsik, 1890: 70; Brancsik, 1891: 21, pl. 2 fig. 7 (genital organs).
- Helicigona pouzolzi bosniensis* – Knipper, 1939: 404, fig. 26 (distribution).
- Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *pouzolzi* var. *bosniensis* – Westerlund, 1889: 115.
- Helix varronis* – Bourguignat, 1888: 230–232, pl. 3 figs 1–2.
- Helix soccaliana* – Bourguignat, 1888: 235–236.
- Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *soccaliana* – Westerlund, 1889: 116.
- Campylaea* (*Dalmatica*) [sic!] *moratschensis* – Kobelt, 1899: 101–102, pl. 238 fig. 1552.
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *pouzolzi* var. *moracensis* – Sturany, 1913: 50.
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *pellanica* – Kobelt, 1902: 66–67, pl. 264 fig. 1704.
- Campylaea* (*Dinarica*) *diocletiana* – Kobelt, 1902: 67–68, pl. 264 fig. 1705.
- Helix* [*Campylaea*, *Eucampylaea*] *dinarica* + *kuzmici* + *pancici* + *pellanica* + *montenegrina* + *adriatica* + *bosnica* + *varronis* + *tschernagorica* + *diocletiana* + *soccaliana* + *sabljari* + *horatii* + *biagioi*, + *brenoica* + *danilo* + *cantrainei* – Westerlund, 1890: 18–21.

Studied specimens. — **Albania:** Dibrë County: W of Shkëmb i Skënderbeut (= 1 km from the Peshkopi-Burrel road towards Fushë-Lurë, 975 m alt., 41.76°N 20.25°E (HNHM 96793/1 juv.); beneath Çidhnë, gorge of Pr. i. Setës, at hydroelectric station, streamside, 510 m alt., 41.76°N 20.25°E (E/1, HNHM 96794/2+1 juv., MMB/1); approximately 1 km W of Çidhnë along path to Gurrë-Lurë, gorge of Pr. i. Setës, 680 m alt, 41.76°N 20.25°E (E/2, HNHM 96795/1+4 juv., MMB/1+1 juv.); same locality, 710 m alt. (E/2, Hu/2, HNHM 96799/1); approximately 2 km W of Çidhnë along path to Gurrë-Lurë, gorge of Pr. i. Setës, in and around an aqueduct, 730–750 m alt., 41.79°N 20.23°E (HNHM 96797/2 juv.); approximately 3 km W of Çidhnë along path to Gurrë-Lurë, gorge of Pr. i. Setës, 730 m alt., 41.86°N 20.23°E (E/2, H/2, HNHM 96798/2); Arras (= 2 km from the Kukës-Peshkopi road towards Çidhnë), 460 m alt., 41.82°N 20.28°E (E/28+7 juv., MMB/28+7 juv., HNHM 95923/1 alc., HNHM 95924/6 alc. + 28 + 7 juv./fragment, NMBE 527495/4+1 juv.); same spot, 500 m (E/12+2 juv., Hu/10+2 juv. +2 fragment, HNHM 96800/10+4 juv./fragment); S of Zall-Reç (= 5 km S of the bridge of the Lumi i Drinit të Zi), 510 m alt., 41.82°N 20.31°E (HNHM 96796/1 juv.). Mat County: Dejë Mountains, Macukull, rocky forest E (= above) of the village, 1280 m alt., 41.72°N 20.13°E (HNHM/1 alc.); appr. 5 km N of Qafemurrë Village, 1607 m alt., 41.65°N 20.17°E (HNHM/1 alc.); Dejë Mountains, limestone hill above the spring section of Varoshit stream, 1540 m alt., 41.79°N 20.2°E (HNHM/1 alc.). Mirditë County: 21 km from Shkodër-Kukës main road towards Thirrë, 970 m alt., 41.03°N 20.20°E (HNHM 96801/1

juv.). **Pukë County:** 3 km N of Milisk (= 16 km S of Fierzë), 567 m alt., 41.27°N 20.08°E (HNHM/1 juv.). **Shkodër County:** Zogaj Village (= W of Shkodër), approximately 5 m alt., 42.0728°N 19.3932°E (NMBE 527516/5+3 juv.); 6 km S of the Vermosh junction on the Shkodër-Gusinje road, 42.65°N 19.73°E (HNHM/3, NMBE 527566/1).

Bosnia-Herzegovina: Neretva (= Narenta) [valley or river] (SMF 80972/2, SMF 29694/7); Bileća, Bilek castle, 42.85°N 18.41°E (SMF 301686/12, Maa/10, NMBE 527515/4+3 body in alc.); Fatnica in Fatničko polje, 43.03°N 18.32°E (SMF 301701/14); 6 km W of Fojnica, near old bridge, 43.24°N 18.30°E (Maa/2); park at Vrelo Bosne (= SW of Sarajevo), 43.81°N 18.26°E (Maa/1); Bjelašnica [Mountain] near Igman Mountain (= S of Sarajevo), 1300 m alt., 43.71°N 18.28°E (Maa/2, S/2 body in alc.); near Kotorac (= 3 km S of Sarajevo), along Željeznica River, 550 m alt., 43.79°N 18.35°E (Maa/2); 6 km N of Trnovo, 800 m alt., 43.72°N 18.41°E (Maa/2, S/2 body in alc.); Čemerno, 43.23°N 18.60°E (HNHM/1 juv.); 2 km S of Dobro Polje, along River Dobropoljanka, 1000 m alt., 43.56°N 18.53°E (Maa/8, S/several bodies in alc.); 2 km S of Tjentište, Sutjeska National Park, along River Priboj, 600 m alt., 43.33°N 18.69°E (Maa/2); Prisoje at Buško blato, 43.69°N 17.07°E (SMF 301690/10); Livno, 43.83°N 17.01°E (SMF 82016/1); hillslope some km from Mrkonjić Grad towards Banja Luka (= near Bjelajce), 420 m alt., 44.4236°N 17.1271°E (NMBE 527492/8+4 juv.); Pliva-waterfall near Jajce, 365 m alt., 44.3375°N 17.2701°E (SMF 301704/3, HNHM/7, NMBE 527567/2+1 (juv.)); Vrbas Canyon 5 km N of Krupa na Vrbasu, 44.67°N 17.14°E (Maa/2); Vrbas Valley at S-margin of Banja Luka, 180 m alt., 44.7462°N 17.1565°E (NMBE 527568/1 juv.); Vinac (= 10 km S of Jajce), castle hill, 44.27°N 17.28°E (SMF 301705/15); Jajce, 44.34°N 17.26°E (SMF 29836/3, SMF 29709/2); Jajce, path to castle ruins, 44.34°N 17.26°E (Maa/1, NMBE 527494 /4); surroundings of the castle of Jajce, 44.34°N 17.26°E (Maa/12); “Dobranje, Narenta”, 42.98°N 17.68°E (SMF 82017/2; SMF 29726/2); floating debris of Popovo polje River near Turkovici, at 20 m water level, 42.92°N 17.88°E (SMF 301706/42, NMBE 527489/4); Gubavica at S rim of Mostarsko polje, 43.21°N 17.83°E (SMF 301692/2); Orahov Do (= 5 km W of Zavala), 42.82°N 17.92°E (Maa/3); Popovo polje near Zavala, limestone area, 42.84°N 17.98°E (Maa/3); Ravno in Popovo polje, oak forest S of the village, 345 m alt., 42.88°N 17.96°E (HNHM/1); Mostar, 43.33°N 17.80°E (coll. C. Bosch SMF/3); Jablanica at Neretva River (= Narenta), 43.65°N 17.75°E (SMF 80987/5; SMF 29701/2); mountain slope 10.8 km from Dubrovica direction Jablanica, 410 m alt., 44.0887°N 17.8925°E (Maa/2, NMBE 527541/7+5 juv./damaged); “Jablanica, Sarajevo” (SMF 29826/3); Travnik, 44.23°N 17.67°E (SMF 29722/2, HNHM/2, SMF 82018/1, SMF 82029/5, SMF 82015/2, SMF 207586/2; SMF 279393/2); Travnik, S-slope of Vlašić Mountain, above castle, 44.23°N 17.67°E, (SMF 80977/2, SMF 301703/4+5 juv.); Travnik, Vlašić Mountain, 1100 m alt., 44.24°N 17.67°E (Maa/2); ditto, 1500 m alt., 44.25°N 17.65°E

(Maa/12, NMBE 527497/2+8 body in alc.); above Travnik, 750 m alt., 44.2355°N 17.6721°E (NMBE 527491/4+4 juv./damaged); Salkinertjena, above Suhidol at Vlašić near Travnik (SMF 80976/2); Drventograd near Travnik (SMF 82021/6, SMF 80975/3); Ivan Mountains, Gojanovac N-slope near cave (SMF 279392/2); Livno, bank of Šnica River at N-border of Livansko polje (SMF 301702/12); Svetlo Borje (SMF/1); Zablianika at Neretva River (= Narenta) (SMF 80997/5); Trebinje, Aleksina medja (SMF 301677a-e/33; SMF 278387/4); Zujevica Valley (= W of Sarajevo) (SMF 29696/2); Igman Mountains S of Sarajevo, 700 m alt. (Maa/3, S/6 body in alc.); Igman Mountains near Sarajevo (SMF 29698/1).

Croatia: Dubrovnik (= Ragusa) (SMF 29706/2, 29714/2, 29719/2, 80676/5, 29692/1, 80959/2, 29704/3, 29723/1, 29708/1+1 juv., 207580/1); Dubrovnik (= Gravosa/Lapad) (SMF 80978/3); Dubrovnik-Lapad, 42.65°N 18.06°E (SMF 207583/3, SMF 207581/1); Dubrovnik-Lapad, in garden of “Lapadska obala 45” and on limestone rocks in W part of Lapad, 42.6568°N 18.0823°E (NMBE 527716/2+1 alc.); Dubrovnik, outside of Ploče archway, 42.6421°N 18.1116°E (SMF 301685/4); Dubrovnik-Gruž (= Gravosa), 42.65°N 18.09°E (SMF 28819/2); Dubrovnik-Gruž (= Gravosa), Ombla River, 42.67°N 18.13°E (SMF 29724/1); Ombla Valley near Dubrovnik, 42.67°N 18.13°E (SMF/3, 29702/1); caves near Ombla spring in Komolac near Dubrovnik, 42.6762°N 18.1363°E (Maa/2); Komolac in Ombla Valley (= N of Dubrovnik), in water 50 m from the spring, 42.6755°N 18.1369°E (NMBE 527547/1, NMBE 527560 /2 juv.); Komolac Village (= N of Dubrovnik), below chapel, 42.6685°N 18.1340°E (NMBE 527546/2+5 juv.); Sustjepan in Ombla Valley (= N of Dubrovnik), grotto at the highway, 42.6709°N 18.1013°E (NMBE 527557/5, HNHM/2 juv., NMBE 527715/1); Dubrovnik, surroundings of Camping “Solitudo” in Lapad, 42.66°N 18.07°E (Maa/4 + 6); Kupari (= E of Dubrovnik), 42.62°N 18.19°E (S/10 alc.); between Dubrovnik and Mlini (= “Ragusa” and “Molini di Breno”) (SMF 80971/2); Mlini, 42.62°N 18.19°E (SMF 207584/2); Biokovo slope above Makarska, 43.29°N 17.02°E (SMF 80985/4); between bifurcation Vošac [Mountain] and Sv. Jure [Mountain], 3 km of junction Vošac, 1483 m alt., 43.33°N 17.05°E (SMF 335583/1 juv.); Pelješac Peninsula, Orebić, 42.97°N 17.17°E (SMF 29703/1); Pelješac Peninsula (= Sabbioncello), Sv. Ilija Mountain (= Vipera) (SMF 207577/2); ditto, 750-960 m alt. (NMBE 527517/23+3 juv.); Sv. Ilija Mountain, above Stanković Village, 42.98°N 17.19°E (SMF 301700/1); Pelješac Peninsula, SE slope of Sv. Ilija Mountain near Orebić, 500 m alt., 42.99°N 17.17°E (Maa/3); Pelješac Peninsula, 200 m from the highway Orebić-Potomje direction Žakotarac, 330 m alt., 42.9661°N 17.3025°E (NMBE 527551/1); Pelješac Peninsula, Županje Selo, quarry, 42.97°N 17.29°E (HNHM/2 juv.); Pelješac Peninsula, border of Trpanj Village direction Orebić, on limestone rocks, 50 m alt., 43.0017°N 17.2765°E (NMBE 527553/1); Rudine at Baćinsko Blato near Metković, 43.07°N

17.40°E (SMF 301691/1); Vrljka (= Verlicca), 43.90°N 16.39°E (SMF 29824/4, SMF 334771/4); Vranjača cave near Dugopolje (= N of Split), 43.57°N 16.63°E (Maa/1); Pelješac Peninsula, Zagorje Mountains, mountain Čarović N side, 600 m from Zaradeže direction Orebić, 370 m alt., 42.8597°N 17.5410°E (NMBE 527514/2+2 juv.); Mljet Island, Sobra, 42.73°N 17.59°E (HNHM/1); Mljet Island, harbor of Sobra, 42.7368°N 17.6005°E (NMBE 527563/3 juv.); Mljet Island, in a grotto 200 m E of Sobra, 40 m alt., 42.7368°N 17.6005°E (NMBE 527719/2 juv.); Mljet Island, halfway between Sobra and Babino Polje, right side of the road, 42.7316°N 17.5791°E (NMBE 527714/1 juv.); Majkovi near Slano, 42.77°N 17.91°E (SMF 80970/1); Slano, 42.78°N 17.89°E (SMF 207579/1 juv.); Trsteno, 42.71°N 17.97°E (SMF 279390/2, 279389/2).

Montenegro: seashore near Sutorina River, 42.44°N 18.50°E (Maa/4, S/2 body); deposits of Sutorina River S of Igalo near Herceg Novi, 42.4491°N 18.5040°E (NMBE 527561/6 juv.); N-exposed hill slope south of crossroads Sutorina-Njivice-Igalo (= W of Herceg Novi), 42.4570°N 18.4919°E (NMBE 527564/4 juv., S 20254/2+2 juv.); Herceg Novi (= Castelnuovo), 42.45°N 18.53°E (SMF 279388/2); Herceg Novi, Forte Mare castle, 42.4501°N 18.5360°E (NMBE 527571/9); Herceg Novi, Kanli kula castle, 42.4522°N 18.5381°E (SMF 227566/2, NMBE 527544/4); N rim of Herceg Novi, on S- and SW-walls of Španjola castle, 160 m alt., 42.4621°N 18.5326°E (NMBE 527565/5+9 juv.); “Vratto” near Herceg Novi (= Castelnuovo) (SMF 80989/2); above Kameno (= NW of Herceg Novi), 620 m alt., 42.4899°N 18.5364°E (NMBE 530920/44+9 juv.); Radošćak [Mountain], 1000 m alt., 42.49°N 18.56°E (SMF 81001/6); NW-rim of Mokrine (= NNW of Herceg Novi), 520 m alt., 42.5143°N 18.4873°E (NMBE 527575/46+28 juv., S 20695/28+2 juv., NMBE 527573/6+2 juv., NMBE 527576/40+6 juv. +1 alc.); 4.2 km NW of Mokrine (= towards Trebinje), 770 m alt., 42.5322°N 18.4671°E (NMBE 527549/3); 7.5 km N of Mokrine (= towards Vrbanje), 1005 m alt., 42.5492°N 18.5058°E (NMBE 527556/3); Orjen [Mountain], 1250 m alt. (SMF 80984/2); Kotor (= Cattaro), 42.42°N 18.77°E (SMF 80950/1, 29707/2, 29691/36, 80973/4, 207582/1, 207587/1, SMF 29729/1); Kotor, 100 m alt., 42.42°N 18.77°E (SMF 80963/2); Kotor (= Cattaro), Kotor, castle hill, 42.42°N 18.77°E (SMF 80952/1, 301688a-c/19); “Path to Montenegro”, 42.42°N 18.77°E (SMF 29699/1); Path Kotor-Njeguši, 42.42°N 18.77°E (SMF 80951/1); Kotor, Spiljara gorge, 42.42°N 18.77°E (SMF 301689a-f/40, SMF 279386/12); Kotor, on castle walls and from a creek, 45 m alt., 42.4263°N 18.7747°E (NMBE 527519/2+1 alc.); Kotor, near S walls of the castle, 15 m alt., 42.4224°N 18.7715°E (NMBE 527500/14+1 juv.; S/4 alc.); mountain slope at SE-rim of Kotor-Škaljari, 150 m alt., 42.4130°N 18.7615°E (NMBE 527502/4+1 juv.); mountain slope at SW-rim of Kotor-Škaljari, 200 m alt., 42.4116°N 18.7623°E (NMBE 527508/2); valley N of Perazića Do (= W of Petrovac), 100 m alt., 42.2133°N 18.9294°E (NMBE 527506/3+4 juv.); N-rim of Rije-

ka-Reževići (= W of Petrovac), 170 m alt., 42.2281°N 18.9132°E (NMBE 527507/4+4 juv.); 2.5 km after bifurcation at Budva in direktion Cetinje, 42.28°N 18.85°E (Maa/1); Budva, 42.28°N 18.83°E (SMF 207576/1, 207585/2, SMF 29816/1); Lovćen [Mountain] near Kotor (SMF 207578/1); ditto, 1100 m alt. (SMF 80983/1); ditto, 1400 m alt. (SMF 80982/3); Ivanova aluga, foot of Lovćen Mountain, 42.38°N 18.83°E (SMF 29810/2); Cetinje, castle park, 42.38°N 18.92°E (SMF 301707/21, Maa/5); Lovćen-Cetinje, 850 m alt., 42.38°N 18.89°E (SMF 81000/1); S of Njeguši (= between Kotor and Cetinje), beside cave “Mandulja pećina”, 900 m alt., 42.4302°N 18.8128°E (NMBE 527550/2 alc.); Spic Mountain (= Spizza) N of Sutomore, 42.14°N 19.05°E (SMF 29725/2, 80960/3, 279391/1); Petrovačka gora Mountains S of Virpazar (Maa/1, S/1 body); Petrovac na Moru, 42.20°N 18.94°E (S 15127/4); Petrovac na Moru, cave near road towards Bar, 42.20°N 18.95°E (SMF 301693/4, 301694/4); SW-rim of Buljarica, 50 m alt., 42.1998°N 18.9607°E (NMBE 527509/40); Paštrovići-Mountains, junction Petrovac-Virpazar-Gluhi Do, 600 m alt., 42.2171°N 19.0219°E (NMBE 527559/1); 3 km S of Paštrovići-Mountains, 500 m alt. (Maa/2); village Komarno near Trnovo village, Spila cave, 300 m alt. (NMBE 527555/1); near Obodska cave (= W of Rijeka Crnojevića), 110 m alt., 42.3520°N 19.0053°E (NMBE 527542/1); tunnel near Ujtin (= NW of Ulcinj), 41.98°N 19.15°E (HNHM/7); Stari Bar, 42.09°N 19.13°E (MMNH/1); Stari Bar, castle walls, 42.09°N 19.13°E (HNHM/4); gorge NE of Stari Bar, limestone rocks, 200 m alt., 42.0974°N 19.1381°E (NMBE 527554/1); Rumija Mountains, E-rim of Tuđemili, 300 m alt., 42.1323°N 19.1434°E (NMBE 527505/1+1 damaged); Rumija Mountains, 1 km from Tuđemili towards Virpazar, 395 m alt., 42.1373°N 19.1398°E (NMBE 527490/1 juv.); 1.6 km from Sutorman pass towards Virpazar, 615 m alt., 42.1713°N 19.0982°E (NMBE 527496/1+1 juv.); Virpazar, 42.24°N 19.09°E (SMF 80957/3, 29711/1, 29823/2); Virpazar, behind hill with monument, 13 m alt., 42.2457°N 19.0926°E (NMBE 527493/4+2 juv.); Virpazar, bifurcation to Rijeka Crnojevića, 42.24°N 19.08°E (SMF 301695/2); E of Virpazar, on the way to Seoca village, above Skadarsko Lake, 85 m alt., 42.2249°N 19.1250°E (NMBE 527543/1+2 juv.); 1 km S of Gluhi Do, karstic rocks, 50 m alt., 42.2270°N 19.0654°E (NMBE 527503/22+8 juv.); D. Selo village (= S of Virpazar), karstic rocks, 50 m alt., 42.2057°N 19.0559°E (NMBE 527498/1+1 juv.); Rumija Mountains, tunnel SE of Boljevići (= approximately 17 km from Tuđemili towards Virpazar), 480 m alt., 42.1829°N 19.1091°E (NMBE 527540/3); Limljani above Gluhi Do in Crimnica Valley, 42.19°N 19.10°E (SMF 301696/4); Rumija Mountains, 17 km from Tuđemili towards Virpazar, 480 m alt., 42.1829°N 19.1091°E (NMBE 527511/5); Jabukov do cave S of Komarno (= NNW of Virpazar), in cave and on limestone rocks nearly the cave, 42.2736°N 19.0703°E (SMF 301699/5, NMBE 527510/8+2 juv.); Žabljak at Skadarsko Lake (= Skutari), 42.31°N 19.15°E (SMF 29705/3, 29821/4, 80986/2, 80992/1,

207588/1, 279394/3, 80996/3); Podgorica-Cetinje road, at bifurcation to Gradac village, 42.39°N 19.11°E (HNHM/2); 3 km from Barutan direction Rijeka Crnojevica (= highway Titograd-Rijeka Crnojevica), 220 m alt., 42.3828°N 19.1022°E (NMBE 527717/1+2 alc.); between Zoganje and Klezna, 41.96°N 19.26°E (HNHM/4); Rumija Mountains, 4 km S of Arbneš/Arbneshi along the road (= approximately 2 km S of pass), 350 m alt., 42.0583°N 19.3535°E (NMBE 527558/1); Kurioci Village (= NW-part of Skadarsko-Lake), 42.3132°N 19.1885°E (NMBE 527520/46+5 juv. +5 alc.); road Risan-Herceg Novi (SMF 80994/2); 8 km from Kameno towards Crkvice (= N of Herceg Novi), 1010 m alt., 42.4880°N 18.5813°E (NMBE 527545/3); NW-rim of Lipci in Kotor-Bay, 50 m alt., 42.4980°N 18.6543°E (NMBE 527501/5); Krivošije (= Crivosije, landscape at SW of Montenegro) (HNHM/1, SMF 29815/4, 5193/1, 5219/1, 29814/2, 80995/2); Maglič Mountain (= Bušat), 1800 m, 42.60°N 19.58°E (SMF 80991/1); Krivošije (= Crivosije), Fort Crkvice, 42.56°N 18.63°E (SMF 5210/1, 80990/2); Krivošije, outlier of Pazua [Mountain] (SMF 80988/2); Vilina pećina u napode cave near Knežlac (= 15 km from Risan direction Crkvice), 42.55°N 18.64°E (Maa/5; SMF 301698/6); 1 km from Viluse direction Trebinje, in forest on Skorča Mountain, 1000 m alt., 42.7159°N 18.5828°E (NMBE 527504/1+5 juv.); Perast, Kotor Bay, 42.48°N 18.69°E (SMF 80993/3); ditto, 50 m alt., 42.48°N 18.70°E (SMF 80999/1); ditto, 100 m alt., 42.48°N 18.70°E (SMF 80966/2); between Kotor and Perast, 20 m alt. (SMF 80965/1); above Banja monastery in Kotor-Bay, (= between Risan and Perast), 50 m alt., 42.5028°N 18.6948°E (NMBE 527562/1 juv.); NW-rim of Orahovac, some m alt., 42.4901°N 18.7532°E (S 20502/2); Ljuta spring in Kotor-Bay (= S of Orahovac), limestone rocks, 5-15 m alt., 42.4862°N 18.7671°E (NMBE 527499/14+3 juv.); Dobrota, 42.46°N 18.76°E (SMF 80955/5); Risan near Kotor (= Cattaro), 42.51°N 18.70°E (SMF 80958/2, 80962/2, 80968/2); near Risan in Kotor Bay and cave “Sopot slop”, 40 m alt., 42.5136°N 18.6816°E (NMBE 527718/2 juv.); Njeguši, 42.43°N 18.81°E (HNHM/1); S of Njeguši Village, entrance of cave in polje, 42.43°N 18.81°E (Maa/7+1 juv.); near Orlina (= SE of Nikšić), S banks of lake Vrtac, 625 m alt., 42.7493°N 18.8783°E (NMBE 527572/2+5 juv./damaged); between Mratinje and Plužine, above Piva River, 43.16°N 18.81°E (HNHM/3); 1 km N from bifurcation to Mratinje, 43.27°N 18.81°E (HNHM/1 juv.); near Piva bridge at Kruševo (= S of Foca), 43.29°N 18.85°E (Maa/3); above Nikšić, 42.76°N 18.95°E (HNHM/3+4 juv.); Lukovo near Nikšić, 42.80°N 19.02°E (SMF 301687/6); Vojnik Mountains, 6 km E of Jasenov polje along the road to Žabljak, 1241 m alt., 42.89°N 19.03°E (HNHM/1); Vojnik Mountains, 12 km E of Jasenov polje along the road to Žabljak, 2 km W of the Knovo junction, near tunnel, 1454 m alt., 42.89°N 19.07°E (HNHM/3); Gvozd, 42.86°N 19.07°E (HNHM/1); Šavnik, 42.95°N 19.09°E (HNHM/2); Treskavac Mountains, Šavnik, on the bank of Bukovica creek, 756 m alt., 42.95°N 19.09°E (HNHM/1);

HNHM/2); between Šavnik and Nikšić, 4 km S of Kruševica (= 8 km S of Mokro), 42.87°N 19.08°E (Maa/4, NMBE 527518/2); gorge of Bijela reka 1 km S of Šavnik, river and its side torrent, 856 m alt., 42.94°N 19.10°E (HNHM/2); 1 km S of Gradac (= before Mokro), 42.94°N 19.07°E (HNHM/1); Sinjajevina Mountains, 3 km W of Boan, bank of Bukavica creek along the Šavnik-Kolašin road, 1007 m alt., 42.95°N 19.16°E (HNHM/1); Krnovo, tunnel S-side, 42.89°N 19.07°E (HNHM/1+7); Donja Bukovica, 43.01°N 19.17°E (HNHM/11); Treskavac Mountain, Pošćenje (near Šavnik), at N end of Kanjon Nevidio, bank of Komarnica Reka, 950 m alt., 42.99°N 19.06°E (HNHM/6); Treskavac Mountains, Pošćenje (= near Šavnik), shallow lake N of the village, lakeshore, 1008 m alt., 42.98°N 19.06°E (HNHM/2); Treskavac Mountains, Petnjica (= near Šavnik), Vasiljeva cave, limestone rocks, rocky forest, 1070 m alt., 42.98°N 19.08°E (HNHM/2); Durmitor Mountains, at Valovito Lake near Sedlo, 1800 m alt., 43.09°N 19.07°E (NMBE 527548/2); ditto, 1900 m (Maa/4); surroundings of Crno Lake near Žabljak, 1450 m alt., 43.14°N 19.09°E (Maa/2); between Boan and Tušina Villages (= “Bohan-Tusina an der Tusina-Pira”), 42.94°N 19.20°E (SMF 29813/5, 29828/5); Sinjajevina Mountains, 18 km E of Boan on the Šavnik-Kolašin road, 1441 m alt., 42.89°N 19.38°E (HNHM/1+4 juv.); Sinjajevina Mountains, Gornji Lipovo (= appr. 12 km W of the Podgorica-Bijelo Polje road), spring section of Plašnica stream, 1132 m alt., 42.87°N 19.40°E (HNHM/1 juv.); Sinjajevina Mountains, 7 km NW of Gornji Lipovo, a mountain pass S of Jablanov peak, 1643 m alt., 42.90°N 19.38°E (HNHM/1 juv.); Žijevo Mountains, 2 km N of G. Križanja, a doline near Sumbova cave, 1176 m alt., 42.54°N 19.45°E (HNHM/2); Planinica Mountain 2 km from Veruša towards Mokro, 1270 m alt., 42.62°N 19.53°E (HNHM/1 body); Planinica Mountain SSE of Veruša (= E of Lijeva Rijeka), 1360 m alt., 42.6382°N 19.5265°E (NMBE 527552/2+6 juv./damaged +1 alc.); Sinjajevina Mountains, Bistrica Lipovska (= near Donji Lipovo), Bistrica vrelo, 1069 m alt., 42.86°N 19.47°E (HNHM/2); Ma e Sokolit Mountain, gorge at E-rim of Korita, 1370 m alt., 42.4873°N 19.5492°E (NMBE 527513/3+5 juv./damaged); Kom Mountains, over 2000 m (SMF 80979/3); Kom Mountains, 7 km SE from Veruša on the road to Rikavačko lake, 1442 m alt., 42.61°N 19.55°E (HNHM/2+1 alc.); Žijevo Mountains, Rikavačko lake near Katun Rikavac, alpine lake inflow brook, 1326 m alt., 42.57°N 19.60°E (HNHM/3 juv.); Žijevo Mountains, Katun Ljakovića, 4 km W of Rikavačko lake, 1694 m alt., 42.57°N 19.59°E (HNHM/22+3 juv./damaged); Darman Mountain, 1700 m alt. (SMF 80980/2).

Serbia: “Serbien” (SMF 29716/1); “Southern Serbia”, coll. Moellendorff ex Rolle (SMF 5204/1, 29728/1, SMF/2).

Diagnosis. — Shell large to medium sized (rarely small), with 1–3 bands; often brown-coloured due to the broad, blurred lateral bands; umbilicus wide, perspective; aperture transversely oval, depressed above.

Description. — Shell large to medium sized (rarely small), depressed cone-shaped; colour yellowish-horny with brownish or greenish tinge; three medium brown to chestnut brown bands, central band narrow and sharply defined, marginal bands often much wider and blurred towards the suture or umbilicus, in many shells, only the clearly separated central band is visible; protoconch 1.5–1.75 whorls; subsequent whorls sculptured with dense, slightly raised, curved, irregular radial riblets; last whorl with slightly depressed, dense spiral grooves; radial stripes becoming increasingly coarser as the number of whorls increases; whorls 4.75–6.5, regularly increasing; last whorl 1.25–2.1 times as wide as the penultimate, descending in a slight curve before the aperture; suture slightly deepened, with an irregular edge; umbilicus usually wide, perspective, regularly increasing in width from the beginning, at the last whorl, umbilicus expanding to one and a half to double the width of the last whorl reaching a width of 3.75–9.4 mm; aperture almost transversely oval, flattened at the top, broadly cut out on the left; insertions 6.25–17.5 mm apart, connected by a very thin callus; apertural margin 1–1.5 mm wide at the side and at the base, slightly extending towards the umbilicus and slightly covering it.

Anatomical features (based on 31 specimens from Albania, Arras (4), Dejë Mountains, 1540 m alt; (1); Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2 km S of Dobro Polje (4), Bileća (1); Croatia, Dubrovnik-Lapad (1), Kupari (4); Montenegro, 3 km from Barutan direction Rijeka Crnojevića (2), cave Mandulja S of Njeguši (2), Kotor, castle (5), Kurioci (5), 2 km from Veruša towards Mokro (1), Planinica Mountain SSE of Veruša (1), 7 km SE of Veruša (1). — Head and dorsum dark grey to grey-brown, flanks and tail lighter; sole dirty white to grey or grey-brown, edges darker; mantle with irregular, blurred, elongated grey or grey-brown spots, its pigmentation often sparse; secondary ureter 31–80 mm long, completely open; penis short tubiform, shorter than epiphallus, flagellum 1.5–3.2 times longer than the penis + epiphallus, epiphallus sometimes with grey pigment proximally; penial lumen structured with narrow, irregular longitudinal folds distally to the papilla, outer wall of the inner penis tube sometimes finely pigmented light grey; penis papilla short, bluntly conical, distally with fine transverse folds or slightly oblique longitudinal grooves, proximally with fine annular folds; papilla opening at the bottom in a lateral longitudinal fissure, starting from the base at about $\frac{1}{3}$ – $\frac{1}{2}$ of the total length and reaching almost to the apex of the papilla, lower end of this fissure sometimes limited by a short transverse cleft; glandulae bifurcated, 3–4 times as long as the dart sac, bifurcated on ca. 60–80 % of their total length, occasionally undivided glandulae or glandulae with three branches occurring, glandulae sometimes slightly brownish; shaft of the bursa copulatrix is $\frac{1}{4}$ – $\frac{1}{10}$ of the length of the pedunculus; diverticulum of equal length up

to 1.6 times longer than pedunculus + vesicle; atrial papilla starting at the genital opening with a broad, slightly raised trunk divided by longitudinal grooves, fan-shaped in the middle of the atrium, outer edge of the atrial papilla bulge-like raised and running in an arc from the vagina along the entrance of the penial lumen back to the genital opening; dart 4.2–6.7 mm long, broad, straight, its crown three times as wide as at the narrowest point above the apex, the lance-shaped apex reaching 40–48 % of the total length, rapidly to moderately widening, slowly tapering, the medium brown to chestnut brown spine with 3–7 ridges.

Measurements (n= 217). — H = 11–32; D = 22–50; AH = 10–26; AD = 11–27.5; measurements of holotype: H = 23.5; D = 43.5; AH = 19.5; AD = 22.

Differential diagnosis. — *D. serbica* is considerably smaller than *D. pouzolzii*. The larger *D. serbica* shells can be recognized by their more conical shape. They are taller than the *D. pouzolzii* shells with the same width. They also have a narrower umbilicus and an almost circular aperture. *Dinarica skutariensis* can be distinguished from the more spherical shells of *D. pouzolzii* by its smaller, thinner-shelled shell. Smaller *pouzolzii* specimens are wider with the same shell height. The umbilicus is narrower in *D. skutariensis* and the spiral grooves on the last groove are weaker.

Remarks. — The specimens available to Bourguignat in 1888 seem to have been mixed up. *Helix soccaliana* Letourneux, 1887 represents a light-coloured variant of the *D. pouzolzii* form, which occurs on the Dalmatian coastal strip between Dubrovnik and Kotor. In the first description, its type locality was erroneously provided as “Santi Deko” on the island of Corfu. However, *D. pouzolzii* has never been found on that island. The type locality of *Helix brenoica* has originally been given as the valley of the Breno (= valley of the Župa river E of Dubrovnik). However, the label of the syntype MOLL-MHNG 17174 reads Kotor (= Cattaro) and shows the characteristics of the *D. pouzolzii* form living there. The syntype of *Helix kuzmici* (MOLL-MHNG 17182) also represents a specimen of the *D. pouzolzii* form from Cattaro, while Bourguignat recorded it from “Ragusa” (= Dubrovnik). The syntypes of *Helix adriatica* MHNG 17172 are recorded from “Environ de Cattaro”, while MHNG 17171 correctly originates from Split (= Spalato). This three-banded, flattened form was also found there by other malacologists, so its record from Kotor is wrong. In the surroundings of Kotor only the large, thick-shelled, mostly brown-coloured *D. pouzolzii* form has been found so far.

Dinarica pouzolzii is a highly variable species explaining the multitude of synonym names describing some rather stable geographic forms. They colonize certain areas of the distribution range but are connected to the other forms by countless transitions. The most widespread form is the one to which the holotype belongs (Fig. 2A). It has three

Fig. 25. Distribution of *Dinarica (Dinarica) pouzolzii* (Deshayes, 1831) and *D. (Sabljaria) stenomphala* (Menke, 1830).

narrow, more or less sharply defined bands on a light, yellowish-horn-coloured background. The shell is more depressed and has a wide, perspective umbilicus. It colonizes the southwestern distribution area east of Vrlika through Split, Makarska to the Pelješac peninsula. Large to medium-sized specimens are characteristic here; this form seems to be threatened as the numbers of observed living animals are declining. The similar form consists of small to medium-sized specimens occurring in southern Bosnia-Herzegovina and over a large area in the hinterland of Montenegro to the Albanian border (= form *montenegrina*, Fig. 2G). The form *bosniensis* (Fig. 2D) is also small but more depressed with low whorls. In this form, the marginal colour bands are wider and strongly blurred, the shells appear to be brown. It is found in central Bosnia-Herzegovina in the northwest of the species' distribution area and represents the northernmost populations of *D. pouzolzii*. The *D. pouzolzii* form living along the coastal strip between Dubrovnik and Kotor Bay is large and only slightly depressed. However, like the Bosnian form, it has broad, blurred, brown lateral bands. This form has a narrower umbilicus due to the slightly higher, more inflated coils. These traits continue in the *D. pouzolzii* shells in the Bay of Kotor (Fig. 3A). However, the shells there are thicker, the whorls even higher and the umbilicus somewhat narrower.

Further along the coast in Montenegro, shell shapes resemble those from the Dalmatian coastal strip. The *D. pouzolzii* form occurring in the northern Albanian mountains displays a mixture of shell characteristics of *bosniensis* and the typical form. It is small, somewhat more depressed, with low coils. Its lateral bands are wider and blurred, and its umbilicus is narrower.

Distribution. — *Dinarica pouzolzii* is widespread in Bosnia-Herzegovina south of Banja Luka to Croatian Vrlika and Split in the west. The north-eastern limit of its distribution is found between Banja Luka and Andrijevica at the northern tip of Albania, continuing into Albania as far as Kukës. The eastern border is between Kukës and Peshkopi. The western border is between Peshkopi and Lezhë.

Dinarica (Dinarica) skutariensis spec. nov.

Figs 26, 35

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Helix (Campylaea) montenegrina — sensu O. Boettger, 1886: 36–37 (non Rossmässler) (“Zwei Exemplare von den Sutormorianer Alpen im Walde jenseits der Verschuta”).

Type specimens. — Holotype SMF 329433, Montenegro, Kronistar Mountain S-slope, about 10 km E of Đuravci (= towards Ostros, S of Skadarsko Lake), limestone rocks, 480 m alt., 42.1099°N 19.2318°E. Paratypes: locus typicus (NMBE 527728/2+1 juv.); locus typicus (NMBE 527729/1); locus typicus (NMBE 527731/1 juv.); same spot, W-side of the mountain, approximately 500 m alt., 42.1109°N 19.2321°E (NMBE 527730/1 damaged +4 juv.); gorge 200 m from Krute village towards Ulcinj, limestone rocks, 120 m alt., 42.0018°N 19.2635°E (NMBE 527732/6 juv.). The two specimens from “Sutomorianer Alpen” mentioned by Boettger as *Helix (Campylaea) montenegrina* seem to be lost (not found in SMF).

Diagnosis. — Shell large, globular, with high whorls, narrow umbilicus and broad, dark-brown bands.

Description. — Shell large, slightly depressed spheroidal to globular-conical shape; colour whitish to greyish and yellowish-brown with three broad, brown bands; central band strongly developed on the upper third of the last whorl reaching 1–2.5 mm width, medium to reddish-brown, sharply defined; uppermost band broader and broadening before reaching the aperture, lower band sharply defined at its upper rim, however blurred in umbilical direction and fading into the shell colour; protoconch 1.5–1.75 whorls, delicately granulated at the beginning, later with fine, slightly arched radially arranged fine riblets; shell surface irregularly sculptured with radially arranged riblets, weakly developed on the upper whorls and strongly developed on the lower whorls, last two whorls with faintly to clearly developed spiral furrows; surface sculpture is most distinct on the last whorl; whorls 5.75 to 6.25, regularly increasing; last whorl reaching 1.4–1.85 times the width of the penultimate, obliquely descending before the aperture; suture rather deep with an irregular rim; umbilicus narrow, pointed, not widening from the start, reaching double the diameter at the last whorl ranging from 4.7–5 mm; aper-

ture spheroidal-transversal elliptic, cut out broadly at the left side; insertions 12–13 mm apart connected by a very delicate hardly recognizable callus; apertural rim sharp, laterally somewhat and basally reinforced, about 1.3–1.7 mm width, covering umbilicus to a quarter.

Measurements (n = 4). — H = 23.5–26.3; D = 37.4–40.2; AH = 18–19.8; AD = 20.6–22; holotype: H = 26; D = 40; AH = 19.8; AD = 22.

Anatomical features. — No living animals known.

Differential diagnosis. — *Dinarica serbica* is clearly smaller with a conical shell and lower whorls. The umbilicus is similar but, compared to the shell-size, wider than in *D. skutariensis*. The more spherical shells of *D. pouzolzii*, such as those found around the town of Kotor, are larger and thicker-shelled. Smaller *D. pouzolzii* specimens are wider with the same shell height. They have an umbilicus that is about twice as wide as that of *D. skutariensis*. The spiral grooves on the last whorl are strongly developed in *D. pouzolzii*. *Cattania petrovici* (A. J. Wagner 1914) is normally smaller, with a narrower umbilicus, a distinctively more depressed shell and the apertural insertions are much closer.

Remarks. — Boettger (1886: 36) erroneously identified this taxon with *Helix montenegrina* Rossmässler, 1838. He had two specimens from the Rumija Mountains (= Sutomorian Alps) at his disposal and compared them with *D. pouzolzii* from this mountain and with his *H. serbica* var. *unitaeniata*. Unfortunately, we are unable to locate his original specimens in his collection in SMF. For this reason, the description of *D. skutariensis* is based on newly collected specimens from the Sutomorian Alps.

Derivatio nominis. — The etymology uses the former name of the Skadar Lake (Lake Skutari), which is in the direct vicinity of the locus typicus.

Distribution patterns. — Only known from a few localities in the Rumija Mountains, south of Lake Skadar in Montenegro.

Fig. 26. *Dinarica (Dinarica) skutariensis* spec. nov. Holotype SMF 329433, Montenegro, Kroništár Mountains, D = 40 mm. Photo original size.

Dinarica (Dinarica) serbica (Kobelt, 1872)

Figs 27–32, 35

Helix serbica Kobelt, 1872: 130–131, pl. 4 figs 7–9. Type locality: “in die serbischen Gebirge”. Holotype SMF 5205 (Fig. 27), “SW-Serbia”.

Helix (Campylaea) serbica f. *unitaeniata* O. Boettger, 1885: 69–70. Type locality: “in dem Walde ober Spitzta-Sutomore auf montenegriner Gebiet in beiläufig 8000’ Meereshöhe unter faulem Holz gesammelt”. Holotype lost.

Helix [Campylaea, Eucampylaea] serbica var. *roschiti* West-
erlund, 1889: 116. Type locality: “Svelto Borje in Bos-
nien”. Type material: not found. Note: name attributed
to Kimakowicz.

Campylaea (Dinarica) serbica var. *major* Kobelt, 1902:
68–69, pl. 265 fig. 1712 (Fig. 29). Type locality: “von
der Südwestspitze Montenegros”. Holotype SMF 5206,
“Southwest Montenegro”.

Campylaea roschitzi Kobelt, 1902: 69, pl. 266 figs 1716–1716a
(Fig. 28). Note: unjustified emendation of *roschiti* West-
erlund, 1889.

Campylaea (Dinarica) nikitai Kobelt, 1906: 60, pl. 330 fig.
2067 (incorrectly in text as fig. 2065!). Type locality: “zwi-
schen Kolasin und Andrievic im Moratschgebiet in Mon-
tenegro, in Buchenwald”. Holotype SMF 5208 (Fig. 30),
Moracha Mountains between Kolašin and Andrijevica.

Campylaea (Dinarica) nikitai var. *fagorum* Kobelt, 1906:
60–61, pl. 330 fig. 2068 (incorrectly in text as fig. 2066!).
Type locality: “zwischen Kolasin und Andrievic im
Moratschgebiet in Montenegro, in Buchenwald”. Holo-
type SMF 5209 (Fig. 31), Moracha Mountains between
Kolašin and Andrijevica, coll. Kobelt ex Wohlberedt.

Chresonyms:

Helix serbica – Kobelt, 1875: 5–6, pl. 93 fig. 982; Bourguignat,
1888: 226; Brancsik, 1891: 21, pl. 2 fig. 10 (genital organs).

Helix [Campylaea, Eucampylaea] serbica – Tryon, 1888: 88,
pl. 21 figs 66–68; Westerlund, 1889: 116.

Helix [Campylaea, Eucampylaea] serbica var. *unitaeniata* –
Tryon, 1888: 88; Westerlund, 1889: 116.

Helix serbica var. *roschitzi* – Brancsik, 1890: 70.

Helix (Campylaea) serbica – Kobelt, 1895: 797–798, pl. 219
figs 5–6.

Campylaea (Dinarica) serbica – Kobelt, 1902: 68, pl. 266 figs
1714–1715; Sturany & Wagner, 1914: 48–49, pl. 4 fig. 26A
(genital organs), pl. 5 figs 28a–b (jaw & dart).

Campylaea (Dinarica) pouzolzi subsp. *serbica* (including
var. *nikitai/nicitai*) – Wohlberedt, 1909: 645–646, pl. 48
figs 51, 56, pl. 49 figs 57–58.

Campylaea pouzolzi var. – Pavlović, 1912: 74–75 (partim).

Campylaea (Dinarica) pouzolzi serbica var. *nikitai* – Stur-
any, 1913: 50.

Helicigona serbica – Knipper, 1939: 404–406, fig. 26 (dis-
tribution); Knipper, 1941: 178; Jaeckel, 1954: 87; Dhora &
Welter-Schultes, 1996: 166 + map; Welter-Schultes, 2012:
600 + figs (shell; distribution).

Campylaea pouzolzi – Tomić, 1959: 21 (partim).

Helicigona (Dinarica) serbica – Subai, 1995: 77, figs 6 (shell),
22 (distribution).

Dinarica (Dinarica) serbica – Groenenberg et al., 2016: 56.

Dinarica serbica – Gojšina et al., 2025: 574–576, figs 72,
73A–C (shell), 74 (genitals), 76 (distribution).

Studied material. — **Albania:** **Dibrë County:** 3 km W of
Murrë pass, Shkëmb i Skënderbeut, gorge of stream Varo-
shit, 975 m alt., 41.85°N 20.18°E (HNHM/13+1 juv.); 9 km N
of Çidhnë towards Fushë-Lurë, 42.04°N 20.26°E (HNHM/6
juv.); same locality, beech forest and dry grassland,
rocks, 1330 m alt., 42.04°N 20.26°E (HNHM/2+4 juv.); Krujë
County, Krujë castle hill, 41.51°N 19.79°E (SMF 216259/2 juv.);
Krujë, Skanderbeg castle, 41.51°N 19.69°E (NMW/1+1 alc.);
Krujë, yard of old Skanderbeg castle (SMF 82022/1); Krujë,
castle walls (HNHM/3 juv.); Mal i Krujës Mountain, 650-
850 m alt., 41.51°N 19.79°E (NMW/2+11 all juv.); ditto, 800-
1000 m alt., 41.51°N 19.80°E (HNHM/6+5 juv.); ditto, 900-
1100 m alt., 41.51°N 19.80°E (NMW/6 juv.). **Kukës County:**
Gurri i Shkallës, E of Arrën, (= 33 km S of Shkodër-Kukës
road), 1300 m alt., 41.95°N 20.26°E (HNHM/3 juv.); Arrën (= 32
km S of the Shkodër-Kukës road), 1150 m alt., 42.04°N
20.26°E (HNHM/1); Gurri i Arrënit, E of Arrën (= 35 km S
of Shkodër-Kukës road), 1598 m alt. (HNHM/2+1 juv.); estu-
ary of stream Bushtricë, around river Drin i Zi and the
stream Bushtricë, 305 m alt., 41.96°N 20.35°E (HNHM/1+7
juv.); Tej-Drinit (= 4.5 km from the bridge of river Drin i
Zi), 620 m alt., 42.08°N 20.35°E (HNHM/1 juv.); Skavicë (= 5
km S of the stream Bushtricë inflow), 622 m alt., 42.03°N
20.35°E (HNHM/1); 1 km S of Resk along the Kukës-Peshkopi
road, 690 m alt., 42.07°N 20.38°E (HNHM/1); Kolesjan-Resk,
along the Kukës-Peshkopi road, 1 km N of the Ploshtan
junction, 670 m alt., 42.11°N 20.38°E (HNHM/2); Mali I Gjal-
lica e Lumës, W of the ridge over Bjëshkë, 42.25°N 20.45°E
(HNHM/3+6 juv./damaged). **Mat County:** 3 km N of Qafa e
Shtyllës on the Klos-Elbasan Road (= 1.3 km N of the conj.
to Tiranë), 1500 m alt. (HNHM/1+1 juv.). **Mirditë County:**
Rubik, Fani River right bank, church hill, 41.76°N 19.78°E
(HNHM 86138/5 juv.). **Shkodër County:** Ura e Mesit (= Mesi),
stone bridge, 42.11°N 19.57°E (HNHM/1 juv.); Maranajt
Mountain, 42.19°N 19.59°E (SMF/1); E of Bogë, 1400 m alt.,
42.39°N 19.71°E (NMW/1+9+4 juv. +7 alc.); 1 km E of Bogë,
N-slope, 900–950 m alt., 42.39°N 19.71°E (S/2 alc.); Mal-
ësia e Madhe [Mountains], 8 km E of Bogë, 42.41°N 19.74°E
(HNHM/20+9 juv.); 4 km from Okol towards Q. e Tërthorës,
1200 m alt., 42.43°N 19.73°E (HNHM/1 damaged.); Lepushë,
42.52°N 19.72°E (HNHM/1); 6 km S of the Vermosh junction
on the Shkodër-Gusinje road, bank of stream Lepushë,

Figs 27-31. *Dinarica (Dinarica) serbica* (Kobelt, 1872). **27.** Holotype *Helix serbica* SMF 5205, “SW-Serbia”, D = 27 mm. **28.** Specimen of *Helix serbica* var. *roschitzii*, SMF 5207, D = 27.3 mm. **29.** Holotype *Campylaea (Dinarica) serbica* var. *major*, “Southwest Montenegro”, SMF 5206, D = 35 mm. **30.** Holotype *Campylaea (Dinarica) nikitai* SMF 5208, Moracha Mountains between Kolašin and Andrijeвица, D = 28 mm. **31.** Holotype *Campylaea (Dinarica) nikitai* var. *fagorum* SMF 5209, Moracha Mountains between Kolašin and Andrijeвица, D = 25 mm. Photos original size.

1082 m alt., 42.65°N 19.73°E (HNHM/4+6 juv.); approximately 3 km SE of Lepushë, beneath Maja e Perondisë, 1411 m alt., 42.76°N 19.73°E (HNHM/2+4 juv.). **Tiranë County:** Mali i Dajtit Mountain, 1200 m alt., 41.36°N 19.91°E (HNHM/3); Mali i Dajtit Mountain, 1300 m alt., 41.37°N 19.91°E (HNHM/9+1 juv.); Mali I Dajtit, W slope of Maja e Dajtit, 1300 m alt., limestone rocks, 41.47°N 19.91°E (HNHM/2 juv.); same spot, beech forest, 1450 m alt., 41.47°N 19.91°E (HNHM/1+2 juv.).

FYROM: Radika River left bank, more than 10 km from Debar direction Gostivar, 610 m alt., 41.5540°N 20.6161°E (NMBE 527734/1 juv./damaged); on limestone rocks along Crni Drim River (= S of Lukovo, N of Ohrid), 41.33°N 20.62°E (Maa/2+1 juv.); 11 km behind bifurcation near Trpejca direction Oteševo, 1600 m alt., 40.95°N 20.81°E (Maa/1); 12 km behind bifurcation near Trpejca direction Oteševo, 1600 m alt., 40.95°N 20.82°E (Maa/1, S/2 alc.); Bistra Mountains, Tresonče Village, 41.56°N 20.72°E (MMNH/1); 4 km S of

Mavrovo, 41.61°N 20.74°E (HNHM/5, NMBE 527744/1); Radika gorge 3 km from Mavrovi-Amovi direction Debar, 1150 m alt., 41.7114°N 20.7159°E (NMBE 527737/2); Radika gorge 2 km below Trnica (= Gostivar-Debar Road), 41.71°N 20.66°E (F/2 juv.); Mavrovska gorge approximately 3.5 km below retaining wall near Mavrovo, 41.71°N 20.71°E (F/4); Bistra Mountains, Nikiforovo Village, 41.67°N 20.77°E (MMNH/1 alc.); Šar Mountains, Popova Šapka near Tetovo, approximately 1800 m alt., 42.01°N 20.87°E (IZPAN/1); Canyon Matka, river Treska, 41.93°N 21.30°E (MMNH/1); Sv. Andrej near Skopje (= Ūsküb), 41.95°N 21.29°E (SMF 216260/1).

Greece: Grámmos Mountains, E slope of Epáno Aréna Mountain (= NW of Pefkófito, N of small lake), 1750 m alt., 40.3106°N 20.9137°E (NMBE 527738/1 juv.); isolated limestone hill 1.25 km SW of Dotsikó (= 25 km W of Grevená), N slope 1400 m alt., 40.11°N 21.10°E (RMNH.MOL.82085/2 juv.); 19 km W of Grevená, 2.3 rkm before Aetia along road Anavri-

ta-Aetia, path to spilea toon nymphon, along river, 1000 m alt., 40.0739°N 21.2015°E (RMNH.MOL./3); isolated limestone hill 1.75 km E of Aetia (= 19 km W of Grevená), W slope, 975 m alt., 40.07°N 21.20°E (RMNH.MOL.82101/11).

Kosovo: Rugovska Canyon 2.5 km W of Kučište, 1300 m alt., 42.69°N 20.07°E (Maa/11 + NMBE 527743/3); Rugovska Canyon 19 km W of Peć, 42.69°N 20.12°E (HNHM/4 + NMBE 527736/1); W of Bjelluhe (= Bjelahe, Belluka), gorge along the road to Čakor pass, 42.70°N 20.05°E (HNHM/9); Peć, Rugovska Canyon, 42.66°N 20.24°E (SMF 301711/7); 14 km from Radevo (= Radevc) towards Rožaje, near Kula border station, 1350 m alt., 42.86°N 20.26°E (HNHM/1 juv.); SE slope of Hajla-Planina between Peć and Rožaje, 42.771°N 20.2804°E (NMBE 527735/3 juv./damaged); Novoselo (= Novoselle), Beli Drin Spring (= Burimi I Drinit te Bardhe), limestone rocks, caves, carstic forest, 42.73°N 20.30°E (SMF 301710/2); Ljuboten above tunnel (= 36 km of Uroševac) (F/3); Ljuboten Mountains near Quafëshqipe (= Globočica), tunnel on road Tetovo-Uroševac, 42.20°N 21.17°E (Maa/4).

Montenegro: Ivanova aluga, foot of Lovćen Mountain, 42.38°N 18.83°E (SMF 29832/4); Spic Mountain (= Spizza) near Sutomore, 42.14°N 19.05°E (coll. O. Boettger, SMF 29837/1); Rumija Mountains, 1 km from Tuđemili towards Virpazar, 395 m alt., 42.1373°N 19.1398°E (NMBE 527742/1); Ulcinj, castle, 41.92°N 19.20°E (HNHM/1 juv.); 7 km W of Tara bridge near Ajuge, 43.15°N 19.25°E (Maa/5+1 juv.); Gornja Dobrilovina (= 20 km from Tara bridge direction Mojkovac), near cave, 840 m alt., 43.0383°N 19.3911°E (NMBE 527745/1+1 damaged); Sinjajevina Mountains, 2 km from Tara bridge towards Rasova, 43.15°N 19.28°E (HNHM/1); Han Garaučića (= S of Kolašin), 42.69°N 19.52°E (F/2+1 juv.); Kom Mountains, 2 km N of Veruša on the Kolašin-Lijeva Rijeka road, bank of Tara River and its gallery, 1133 m alt., 42.81°N 19.51°E (HNHM/4); 2 km N of Kolašin, 900 m alt., 42.85°N 19.52°E (Maa/3 + S/1 alc.); in forest at border of Gojakovići (= 800 m from Kaludra direction Mojkovac), 1000 m alt., 42.9925°N 19.4725°E (NMBE 527740/1 juv.); Tara Canyon, 1200 m alt. (HNHM/2 juv.); Tara Canyon 3 km S of Donja Dobrilovina, 43.01°N 19.42°E (Maa/1 + S/1 alc.); 4 km E of Kraljske Bare (= E of Kolašin), 1100 m alt., 42.73°N 19.65°E (Maa/2 + S/4 alc.); Bjelasica Mountains, beside Biogradsko Lake, 1100 m alt., 42.9023°N 19.5944°E (F/2 + NMBE 527746/16+4 juv +2 alc.); ditto, 1200 m alt. (Maa/6); 3.5 km SW from crossroad Mojkovac-Kolašin towards Biogradska Gora, slope above Tara-River, 885 m alt., 42.9068°N 19.5582°E (NMBE 527739/2 juv./damaged); Bjelasica Mountains, Kurikuće, Suvoda potok (= 14 km from the Berane-Kolašin road), 1172 m alt., 43.08°N 19.73°E (HNHM/1 juv.); Prokletije Mountains, Zastan (= approximately 7 km S of Vusanje), W slope of Maja e Brianibunsit, 1370 m alt., 42.60°N 19.81°E (HNHM/2+1 juv.); Prokletije Mountains, 2 km S of Vusanje, Oko and Grlja stream, 1034 m alt., 42.69°N 19.83°E (HNHM/7+2 juv.); Visitor Mountains, 6 km

SW of Murino, gorge of the sidestream of Dasova stream at a sinkhole, 1425 m alt., 42.63°N 19.85°E (HNHM/1+3 juv.); 3 km SE of Grnčar along the Gusinje-Shkodër road, 962 m alt., 42.75°N 19.80°E (HNHM/1); Čakor Pass, 42.66°N 20.00°E (HNHM/2); between Andrijevica and Peć, spring streamlet 9 km after Murino, 1100 m alt., 42.68°N 19.95°E (Maa/2 damaged); NE of Velika (= 11 km from Murino towards Čakor pass), streamside, 42.76°N 19.95°E (HNHM/6+1 juv.); E of Velika (= 18 km from Murino towards Čakor pass), 1554 m alt., 42.76°N 19.95°E (HNHM/4); Rugovska Canyon 26 km W of Peć, along small streamlet, 1300 m alt., 42.68°N 20.04°E (Maa/2); stream valley 27 km from Peć direction Čakor Pass, 42.67°N 20.04°E (F/3); 16 km S of Rožaje, 1700 m alt., 42.76°N 20.20°E (Maa/1); 10 km S of Bać, valley of river Ibar, near cave, 1034 m alt., 42.90°N 20.20°E (HNHM/1); valley of river Ibar (= 1.5 km SW of Špiljani), 829 m alt., karstic forest, 43.01°N 20.33°E (HNHM/2).

Serbia: “Southern Serbia”, coll. Moellendorff (SMF 29839/1+1 juv.); above road approximately 1 km above Raška well near Sopoćani monastery, 43.11°N 20.36°E (F/1).

Bosnia-Herzegovina: “Svetlo Borje”, ex M. v. Kimakowicz (SMF 80998/1).

Diagnosis. — Small shells with three broad, brown bands; surface with strong radial riblets and spiral grooves; umbilicus moderately wide, barely covered by the apertural margin; aperture almost circular.

Description. — Shell small, rarely medium-sized, short-cone shaped, horn-coloured with a brownish or greenish tinge; upper third of the whorls with a 1–1.5 mm wide, medium to dark brown band, above and below the central band with blurred, broad, brown stripes; protoconch of 1.5–1.75 whorls with a slightly wavy radial pattern, subsequent whorls sculptured with dense, coarse, irregular radial stripes, last whorl with slightly deepened, dense spiral grooves, radial stripes become increasingly coarser with increasing whorls; whorls 5.5–6 regularly increasing, last whorl 1.3–1.9 times as wide as the penultimate, descending in a slight curve; suture slightly deepened, with an irregular edge; umbilicus moderately wide, slightly perspective, regularly increasing in width, in the last whorl, umbilicus slightly widening reaching one and a half times the width of the last whorl with a diameter of 2.8–5.6 mm; aperture almost circular, broadly cut out on the left; apertural insertions 8–11 mm apart, connected by a very thin callus; apertural margin sharp, widened 0.5–1.5 mm at the side and at the base, extending towards the umbilicus and slightly covering it.

Measurements (n = 41). — H = 15.3–21; D = 22–33; AH = 10.7–15.5; AD = 12.3–18.

Anatomical features (according to 5 specimens from Albania, 1 km SE of Bogë (2); Serbia, 4 km E of Kraljske Bare (1); FYROM, 12 km behind bifurcation near Trpejca direction Oteševo (2), Fig. 32). — Head and dorsum grey or grey-

Fig. 32. *Dinarica (Dinarica) serbica* (Kobelt, 1872) Albania, 1 km SE Bogë, NMBE. **A.** Body. **B.** Genital organs. **C.** Atrial, penial and vaginal lumen. **D.** Dart in two views.

brown, flanks and tail lighter; sole cream to yellowish, margins light grey; mantle with irregular, blurred, elongated grey-brown spots; secondary ureter 42–45 mm long, completely open; penis short tubiform, shorter than epiphallus, flagellum 2.3–2.6 times longer than the penis + epiphallus, epiphallus sometimes pigmented proximally grey; penial lumen structured by narrow, irregular longitudinal folds up to the papilla; penial papilla short, bluntly conical, covered below with fine transverse folds, the upper half with fine, slightly oblique longitudinal grooves, the opening at the bottom of a lateral longitudinal fissure starting from the base at about $1/3$ – $1/2$ of the total length reaching to the apex of the papilla, lower end of fissure sometimes limited by a short transverse grooves; glandulae forked, 3–4 times as long as the dart sac, bifurcated for 70–80 % of their length, sometimes slightly brownish in colour; shaft of the bursa copulatrix $1/3$ – $1/2$ of the length of the pedunculus, diverticulum 1.3–1.4 times longer than pedunculus + vesicle; close to the genital opening, atrial papilla with a broad, slightly raised trunk divided by longitudinal grooves; fan-shaped in the centre of the atrium, with a bulge-like raised outer

edge; this thickened part about 3 times as high as the flat trunk, forming an arc from the centre of the atrium along the opening towards the penial lumen, and bending back to the genital opening; central part of the bulbous edge is sometimes subdivided into two halves, sometimes with a short, rapidly flattening trunk leading towards the vaginal lumen; dart 4–5.2 mm long, broad, and straight, its crown twice as wide as at the narrowest point above the apex; apex lance-shaped reaching 42–48 % of the total length and rather rapidly widening, slowly tapering; the chestnut-brown spine with 4–7 ridges.

Differential diagnosis. — *Dinarica pouzolzii* can usually be distinguished from *D. serbica* by its size. The small *pouzolzii* specimens are more depressed and are wider at the same shell height. Their umbilicus is wider and increases in width more rapidly from the beginning. Their aperture is oblique, often flattened at the top. *Dinarica skutariensis* is also larger than *D. serbica*. It has a higher spire and therefore a more spherical habit. The umbilicus of *D. skutariensis* is similar to that of *D. serbica* but narrower in relation to its size. *Dinarica albanica* is larger than *D. serbica*. It is

bright horn-coloured without a band and a higher spire. Its surface sculpture is weakly pronounced, and its umbilicus is half covered by the apertural margin. Its aperture is larger, obliquely transverse. *Dinarica stenomphala* is about the same size or larger than *D. serbica*. It has a yellowish-horn-coloured shell with a band; its umbilicus is very narrow and covered by the apertural margin except for a slit. Its surface sculpture is weakly developed; spiral grooves are faint.

Remarks. — *Dinarica serbica* is not very variable. Remarkably, there is a smaller form with a high spire and dark shell colour, which is characteristic of moist and cooler biotopes such as forests, valleys and high mountains. A larger, more depressed, more brightly coloured form is found in drier, warmer biotopes. They appear to represent ecological phenotypes (see Subai, 1995: 77).

Distribution. — This species is widespread in Montenegro approximately east of a line Durmitor Mountains to Kotor Bay. It also inhabits the south-eastern fringes of Serbia and Kosovo, the northern part of Albania and the west of FYROM. In Greece, it is only known from a few sites in the north-western area of the country.

Subgenus *Sabljaria* Brusina, 1904

Sabljaria Brusina, 1904: 162. Type species (by original designation): *Helix stenomphala* Menke, 1830 (monotypic).

Dinarica (Sabljaria) stenomphala (Menke, 1830)

Figs 25, 33–34

Helix stenomphala Menke, 1830: 126. Type locality: “in Croatia”. Type specimens: unknown.

Chresonyms:

Helix stenomphala – Rossmässler, 1838: 14–15, pl. 33 fig. 458; Pfeiffer, 1848: 337; Pfeiffer, 1849/1853: pl. 80 figs 11–12 (1849), page 80 (1852); Pfeiffer, 1859: 268.

Campylaea stenomphala – Brusina, 1869: 50–51; Brusina, 1876: 53; Kormos, 1906: 141; Kormos, 1907: 188; Soós, 1917: 134–135, figs 108 (radula), 109 (genital organs).

Helix (Campylaea) stenomphala – Brusina, 1870: 28.

Helix [Campylaea, Eucampylaea] stenomphala – Tryon, 1888: 88, pl. 21 figs 63–65; Westerlund, 1889: 117.

Helicigona [Campylaea] stenomphala – Hesse, 1931: 68; Knipper, 1939: 406.

Helicigona stenomphala – Welter-Schultes, 2012: 601 + fig. (distribution).

Dinarica (Sabljaria) stenomphala – Groenenberg et al., 2016: 56, 63, figs 3.21 (shell), 4.24 (genitals).

Studied material. — **Croatia**: Velebit Mountains: not spec-

Fig. 33. *Dinarica (Sabljaria) stenomphala* (Menke, 1830). NMBE 527723/5a, Croatia, Velebit Mountains, 8.4 km from the bifurcation Dom Zavižan in direction Oltari, mixed forest with limestone rocks, 1020 m alt., D = 27.7 mm. Photo original size.

ified (NMW/1, SMF/6, 301708/1 + 29452/1 + 29453/2; ditto, coll. Jaeckel, SMF 207589/2; N side of Zavižan Mountain (= 600 m from the bifurcation Dom Zavižan direction Oltari), mixed forest with limestone rocks, 1500 m alt., 44.8208°N 14.9861°E (NMBE 527726/3); 8.4 km from the bifurcation Dom Zavižan direction Oltari, mixed forest with limestone rocks, 1020 m alt., 44.8460°N 14.9930°E (NMBE 527723/5); small deciduous forest 1.3 km N of Oltari (= direction Biljevine), on limestone rocks, 890 m alt., 44.8913°N 14.9758°E (NMBE 527724/5); Veliki Kozjak Mountain E part, mixed forest with limestone rocks, 1200 m alt., 44.7283°N 15.0501°E (NMBE 527741/9+6 juv./damaged); 11 km from Krasno Polje direction Štirovača, in deciduous forest, on limestone rocks, 44.7551°N 15.0886°E (NMBE 529771/6 + 573296/6 alc.); Jadičevac Mountain (= Žadičevac), 44.55°N 15.19°E (HNHM/2 + SMF/2); Morota (SMF/5); “Pajina glavica” (SMF 29451/2); Podgorje promontory, approximately 5 km from Veliki Alan pass direction Jablanac, deciduous forest, on limestone rocks, 1100 m alt., 44.7091°N 14.9625°E (NMBE 527725/1+4 juv.); Zavižan Mountain, 44.80°N 14.97°E (HNHM/2); Oltari (= NW of Krasno), 44.87°N 14.98°E (NMW 63955/1 + HNHM/3); Starigrad, rocks near Rossijev kuk, 1661 m alt., 44.98°N 14.98°E (HNHM/6); above of Bačić dolac (= between Mlinište and Baške Oštarije), 44.57°N 15.10°E (NMWE 21213/2); Štirovača, 44.52°N 15.17°E (HNHM/1 + SMF 82025/1 + 82026/1); forest of Štirovača, 44.69°N 15.04°E (SMF 301709/6); Veliki Kozjak Mountain, 44.73°N 15.03°E (NMWE 21212/2); road Apatišan-Lomska duliba, 44.73°N 15.07°E (NMWE 31103/7 + NMWK 19799/1); Mali Rajinac Mountain, 44.79°N 15.01°E (NMWE 46829/2); Baške Oštarije (= Ostarija), 44.52°N 15.17°E (NMW 2858/4 juv. + 2858a/4+1 juv. + 63956/1 + SMF/3); Metla Mountain, 44.53°N 15.18°E (NMWR/3 + SMF 82027/4 + 82023/4); 2 km on a side road (N of the road near Baške Oštarije), direction Velebit Mountains, mixed forest with limestone rocks, 910 m alt., 44.5337°N 15.1563°E (NMBE

Fig. 34. *Dinarica (Sabljaria) stenomphala* (Menke, 1830) Croatia, Velebit Mountains, 11 km from Krasno Polje in direction Štirovača, NMBE 573296. **A.** Body. **B.** Genital organs. **C.** Atrial, penial and vaginal lumen. **D.** Dart in two views.

527727/5 juv.); Jadovno, 44.54°N 15.24°E (HNHM/2); Brušane, 44.50°N 15.26°E (HNHM/1); Trnovac near Gospić, 44.52°N 15.27°E (SMF 82028/2).

Diagnosis. — Shell spherical conic, horn-yellow coloured; umbilicus narrow, largely covered by the apertural margin; shell surface with fine radial riblets and very faint spiral grooves.

Description. — Shell of depressed spherical conical shape; colour horn yellow with a brownish tinge and a more or less broad, brown band; surface with irregular, fine radial riblets and with weakly pronounced spiral bands; whorls 5.25–6; umbilicus 2–2.8 mm wide, mostly covered by the reflected apertural margin; aperture transversely oval, insertions 9.5–15.8 mm apart; apertural margin sharp, broadly expanding laterally and at the base of the shell.

Measurements (in mm, n= 40). — H = 16.5–24.5; D = 27–35.8; AH = 12.8–18; AD = 16–22.

Anatomical features. — Head and dorsum of the animal dark grey, flanks and tail lighter; sole light grey to grey-

brown, edges darker; mantle on the last whorl with small, roundish, often confluent, grey-brown to black spots; a broad stripe of the same colour present along the long pulmonary vein; spots clearly darker pigmented in front of the mantle edge than on the distal mantle surface; secondary ureter 38–50 mm long, completely open; jaw with 4–6 ridges; penis tubiform, with a slight swelling at the transition between penis and epiphallus; penial lumen structured with broad, moderately high longitudinal folds reaching to the tip of the papilla, and with fine transverse folds next to the papilla; penial papilla short, conical, with well-defined, somewhat oblique transverse grooves; the pore of the papilla opening in a lateral longitudinal fissure extending almost from the base to the apex of the papilla; flagellum is 2–2.75 times longer than the penis + epiphallus; atrial papilla with a moderately broad, moderately raised trunk originating at the genital opening; briefly raised in the centre of the atrium, and bifurcating in two lateral branches leading in direction of the vaginal and penial lumina; a

Fig. 35. Distribution of *Dinarica (Dinarica) skutariensis* spec. nov., *D. (D.) serbica* (Kobelt, 1872) and *D. (D.) albanica* (Jaeckel, 1954).

side branch pointing in direction of the vaginal lumen, and sometimes terminating there; the other side branch ending in front of the penial lumen; a single broad longitudinal fold running parallel to the atrium wall, also extending deeper into the penial lumen; glandulae 4–6 times longer than dart sac, deeply split at 75–85 % of their length; shaft of the bursa copulatrix $\frac{1}{4}$ – $\frac{1}{2}$ of the length of the pedunculus; diverticulum of the same length or slightly shorter than the pedunculus + vesicle; dart 4.65–4.9 mm long, broad, straight; its apex about 35–40 % of the total length, rapidly to moderately widening, somewhat pointed.

Differential diagnosis. — *Dinarica albanica* is larger than *D. stenomphala*. Its umbilicus is wider and only half covered by the apertural margin, and its apertural insertions are closer to each other. *Dinarica serbica* is usually smaller and dark brown in colour. Its surface is sculptured with coarser radial riblets and deeply recessed spiral grooves. It has a wider umbilicus, which is barely covered by the apertural margin. The aperture of *D. serbica* is roundish. *Arianta frangepanii* (Kobelt, 1906), with which

it is supposed to inhabit the Velebit Mountains, is smaller and narrower than *D. stenomphala*. It has a smaller protoconch and lower, more densely coiled whorls. Its shell has $\frac{1}{2}$ whorl or more than *D. stenomphala*. The surface of *A. frangepanii* is granular on the upper whorls. There are no or only very blurred spiral grooves on the last whorl. The umbilicus of *A. frangepanii* is wider and barely covered by the apertural margin. This species has not been found since its description.

Remarks. — *Dinarica (S.) stenomphala* differs in several anatomical traits from the remaining *Dinarica* species. Its mantle pattern consists of small, roundish dabbled spots. Groenenberg et al. (2016) corroborated the separation of *Sabljarja* as a subgenus of *Dinarica*.

The differences in the morphology of the genital organs (if compared to *Dinarica* s. str.) are (1) the short diverticulum, which is of the same length or even shorter than the bursa copulatrix; (2) in *D. stenomphala*, the penial papilla has a lateral fissure extending from the papilla's base to its apex (in *Dinarica* s. str., this fissure stretches from the

apex to the middle of the papilla only); and (3) its dart has a smaller apex in relation to its overall size.

Distribution. — Podgorje promontory and Velebit Mountains at the Croatian Coast.

DISCUSSION

The distribution of the genus *Dinarica* extends across the countries of the former Yugoslavia. *Dinarica* has colonized the region extending from the Banja Luka-Vrlika-Split line in a south-easterly direction to the middle of Albania, a 150–200 km wide strip measured from the Adriatic coast. One species (*serbica*) also reaches Greek territory. The monotypic subgenus *Sabljaria* is endemic to the Velebit Mountains on the eastern side of the Kvarner Bay. According to Wenz (1942: 81), the fossil occurrence of *Dinarica* included *Helix insignis* Zieten, 1832, a snail found in southern Germany, Switzerland and in northern Italy. However, this species from the Middle Miocene proved to be a member of the Elonidae, and not of the Ariantinae (Nordsieck, 2014). There is only one fossil currently included in *Dinarica*, *D. tutovana* (Sevastos, 1922) from the lower Maeotia in Romania, Prahova County. Thus, the fossil occurrence of *Dinarica* also covers the Balkan area, rendering it likely that this group is endemic to eastern Europe. So far, there is no record of the genus inhabiting limestone deficient substrates especially since *Dinarica* species are known to specifically favour calcareous habitats. Moreover, the large, hairless shell distinguishes *Dinarica* from those of similar genera. *Cattania* Brusina, 1904 species are similar in shell appearance but have smaller shells. They can be distinguished by their long, slender penial papilla, which is narrowed in the middle, and by the large, spoon-shaped atrial papilla. *Cattania* species occur northeast and east of the distribution area of *Dinarica*.

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